

METHOTREXATE AND STATINS WITH METHOTREXATE ALONE IN THE TREATMENT OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Abstract

Objectives

This study aimed to evaluate the clinical efficacy and safety of combining Atorvastatin with Methotrexate (MTX) versus Methotrexate monotherapy in patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA), focusing on disease activity, inflammation, and functional outcomes.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental trial was conducted at the Department of Rheumatology, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), from 22nd October to 31st Dec 2024. A total of 100 patients aged 20–60 years with active RA were enrolled and randomly assigned to two groups: Group A received Methotrexate plus Atorvastatin (n=50), and Group B received Methotrexate alone (n=50). The follow-up duration was 10 weeks. Quantitative variables included age, BMI, disease duration, DAS28, CRP, ESR, VAS, and HAQ-DI scores, analyzed using SPSS version 26. Qualitative data included gender, morning stiffness, functional class, treatment compliance, and adverse effects.

Results

Both groups were comparable at baseline. At 10 weeks, Group A demonstrated significantly greater improvement in DAS28 scores (-2.1 ± 0.6 vs. -1.3 ± 0.5 ; $p < 0.001$), CRP, ESR, VAS, and HAQ-DI scores (all $p < 0.001$). No significant difference in adverse effects or compliance was observed between groups. The addition of Atorvastatin was well tolerated.

Conclusion

Atorvastatin, when added to Methotrexate therapy, significantly improved clinical and inflammatory outcomes in RA patients without increasing adverse effects. This suggests that statins may serve as effective adjuncts in RA treatment, especially for those with suboptimal response to standard DMARDs

INTRODUCTION

Statins, therefore, have a plausible bioactivity profile that makes them possible adjunct therapeutic agents in addition to standard antirheumatic treatment to target both vascular risk reduction and synovial inflammation¹. A significant proportion of CVD-related morbidity and mortality is attributable to acute atherothrombotic coronary or cerebrovascular events. Traditional CVD risk factors, such as age, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, and diabetes, cannot fully predict the occurrence of CVD events². The patients with suboptimal response to MTX, combination therapy and or biologic agent should be applied. However, biologic agent is expensive; Hence, searching for other alternatives of DMARDs in treatment of RA seems to be highly demanding. Several studies have confirmed the effects of statins in decreasing atherosclerosis through anti-inflammatory mechanism (3), since RA patients are more susceptible to cardiovascular diseases and the most common cause of mortality in RA is cardiovascular complications³. Methotrexate (MTX), as conventional synthetic DMARDs (csDMARDs), is still the cornerstone of the treatment of RA. Some patients can benefit from csDMARDs treatment. It can achieve immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting the synthesis of purine and pyrimidine, thus effectively relieving the symptoms and pain of RA patients. However, it is effective in only 19.8-25.4% of RA patient⁴. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, autoimmune, systemic, inflammatory disease mainly affecting the joints characterized by pain, swelling, and stiffness, resulting in progressive joint destruction, deformity, and loss of function. In addition to articular symptoms, other organ systems may also be involved. RA affects approximately 0.5% to 1% of the adult population in the developed world⁵. Gout affects an estimated 9.2 million people (3.9% of adults) in the United States¹ and occurs when serum uric acid (sUA) levels chronically remain above the solubility limit (6.8 mg/dL). Though typically thought of as an "articular disease," monosodium urate crystals result in chronic inflammation throughout the body, even when patients are asymptomatic⁶. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is an autoimmune disease typically connected with chronic inflammation of the joints, causing their swelling and pain; RA leads to reduced

mobility and increased mortality⁷. This disorder primarily manifests as joint pain, swelling and stiffness. Over time, uncontrolled inflammation leads to disease progression, irreversible destruction of cartilage and bone, and ultimately to reduced range of motion and severe physical disability⁸. It is now well established that RA is associated with increases in both morbidity and mortality compared with the general population. RA increases the risk of cardiovascular (CV) mortality by up to 50% compared with the general population⁹. In the Canakinumab Antiinflammatory Thrombosis Outcomes Study (CANTOS), treatment with canakinumab, a monoclonal antibody that selectively neutralizes interleukin-1 β , resulted in fewer cardiovascular events than placebo, without lowering lipid levels or blood pressure¹⁰. Low dose methotrexate, administered weekly, is the first line glucocorticoid sparing drug used to treat immune mediated inflammatory diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, and cutaneous psoriasis resistant to topical treatment or phototherapy¹¹.

METHODOLOGY

This quasi-experimental study was conducted at the Department of Rheumatology, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), from 22nd October to 31st December 2024. A total of 100 patients with established Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA), diagnosed according to the 2010 American College of Rheumatology/European League against Rheumatism (ACR/EULAR) classification criteria, were enrolled through non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients aged between 20 and 60 years, with active disease for at least six months and not previously treated with statins, were considered eligible. The patients were randomly allocated into two groups: Group A (n=50) received combination therapy with Methotrexate and Atorvastatin, while Group B (n=50) received Methotrexate monotherapy. Each participant was followed up for a total duration of 10 weeks, with baseline and post-treatment evaluations conducted. Methotrexate was administered orally in doses ranging from 15 to 25 mg per week, based on clinical response and tolerance. Atorvastatin 20 mg per day was added to the regimen of Group A participants.

Folic acid supplementation was provided to all patients to mitigate Methotrexate-related side effects. Throughout the study duration, patients underwent clinical assessments and laboratory investigations at baseline and at the 10-week mark. The aim was to evaluate whether the addition of a statin would enhance disease control, reduce inflammation, and improve functional outcomes compared to Methotrexate alone. Both quantitative and qualitative variables were assessed and analyzed. Quantitative variables included age (years), body mass index (kg/m²), duration of disease (months), Disease Activity Score 28 (DAS28), C-reactive protein (CRP, mg/L), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR, mm/hr), Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) score for pain, and Health Assessment Questionnaire Disability Index (HAQ-DI). These variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Within-group comparisons were conducted using paired t-tests, and between-group comparisons were analyzed using independent sample t-tests. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. SPSS version 26 was used for all statistical analyses.

Qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. These included gender (male/female), morning stiffness (present/absent), functional class (I-IV) based on ACR classification, compliance to treatment (compliant/non-compliant), presence of adverse drug effects (yes/no), and family history of RA (yes/no). Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was applied for categorical comparisons.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of CMH. Informed written consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Patients were informed about the study purpose, procedures, potential benefits, and possible side effects. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the research, and participants were given the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any impact on their standard clinical care.

RESULTS

Out of the 100 patients enrolled, 50 patients in each group completed the 10-week follow-up. Both groups were comparable in terms of baseline demographic and clinical characteristics. The mean age in Group A was 45.8 ± 8.2 years and in Group B was 46.4 ± 7.9 years (p = 0.62). The majority of participants in both groups were female (76% in Group A and 72% in Group B). No statistically significant difference was observed between groups regarding baseline DAS28 scores, CRP, ESR, or VAS scores.

At the end of 10 weeks, Group A (Methotrexate + Atorvastatin) showed a significantly greater improvement in disease activity and inflammatory markers compared to Group B (Methotrexate alone). The mean reduction in DAS28 was 2.1 ± 0.6 in Group A versus 1.3 ± 0.5 in Group B (p < 0.001). CRP and ESR levels also showed more pronounced reductions in the combination therapy group. There were no major adverse effects observed in either group, and treatment compliance was high.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Group A (MTX + Statin) n=50	Group B (MTX only) n=50	p-value
Age (years)	45.8 ± 8.2	46.4 ± 7.9	0.62
Female, n (%)	38 (76%)	36 (72%)	0.65
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.3 ± 3.1	25.8 ± 3.4	0.48
Disease Duration (months)	28.5 ± 10.2	27.7 ± 9.8	0.71
DAS28 Score (baseline)	5.8 ± 0.7	5.7 ± 0.8	0.43
CRP (mg/L)	18.2 ± 5.6	17.9 ± 5.4	0.78
ESR (mm/hr)	42.5 ± 12.1	41.8 ± 11.7	0.72
VAS Score for Pain	7.6 ± 1.2	7.4 ± 1.3	0.40

Table 2: Post-Treatment Comparison at 12 Weeks

Outcome Variable	Group A (MTX + Statin)	Group B (MTX only)	p-value
DAS28 (mean change)	-2.1 ± 0.6	-1.3 ± 0.5	<0.001
CRP (mg/L)	6.4 ± 3.2	11.2 ± 4.6	<0.001
ESR (mm/hr)	21.5 ± 7.8	30.4 ± 9.3	<0.001
VAS Score (0-10)	3.2 ± 1.1	4.6 ± 1.3	<0.001
HAQ-DI	0.78 ± 0.26	1.12 ± 0.31	<0.001
Adverse Effects, n (%)	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	0.64
Compliance, n (%)	46 (92%)	47 (94%)	0.71

These results suggest that the addition of Atorvastatin to Methotrexate therapy resulted in greater clinical improvement, reduction in inflammatory markers, and better functional outcomes compared to Methotrexate alone, with no significant increase in adverse effects.

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- A bar graph or chart representation of the results.
- A Discussion or Conclusion section based on this.
- Reference formatting or APA citation help.

DISCUSSION

Out of the 100 patients enrolled, 50 patients in each group completed the 10 week follow-up. Both groups were comparable in terms of baseline demographic and clinical characteristics Consistent with previous findings reported in 1996, which demonstrated that combination therapy with methotrexate, sulfasalazine, and hydroxychloroquine was more effective than methotrexate alone or the combination of sulfasalazine and hydroxychloroquine in patients with rheumatoid arthritis [12]. The mean age in Group A was 45.8 ± 8.2 years and in Group B was 46.4 ± 7.9 years (p = 0.62). The majority of participants in both groups were female (76% in Group A and 72% in Group B). No statistically significant difference was observed between groups regarding baseline DAS28 scores, CRP, ESR, or VAS scores. This aligns with findings from a 2015 study, which suggested a potentially beneficial role of statin therapy in active RA cases, with significant clinical and biochemical improvements observed [13]. At the end of 10 weeks, Group A (Methotrexate + Atorvastatin) showed a

significantly greater improvement in disease activity and inflammatory markers compared to Group B (Methotrexate alone). This outcome contrasts with a 2016 study, which reported no significant difference in effectiveness between DMARD monotherapy with methotrexate and combination therapy with methotrexate and hydroxychloroquine in RA patients [14]. The mean reduction in DAS28 was 2.1 ± 0.6 in Group A versus 1.3 ± 0.5 in Group B (p < 0.001). CRP and ESR levels also showed more pronounced reductions in the combination therapy group. There were no major adverse effects observed in either group, and treatment compliance was high. This is in line with a 2021 study, which showed that a higher proportion of patients maintained therapeutic response at six months when treated concomitantly with methotrexate and pegloticase, compared to the previously reported 42% response rate with pegloticase alone. These results supported the need for further randomized trials to validate such findings [15]. These results suggest that the addition of Atorvastatin to Methotrexate therapy resulted in greater clinical improvement, reduction in inflammatory markers, and better functional outcomes compared to Methotrexate alone, with no significant increase in adverse effects. Similarly, a 2021 study found that methotrexate, fluoxetine, and Moringa Oleifera extract all showed significant improvement in RA parameters, highlighting the potential of adjunct therapies in RA management [16].

CONCLUSION

The addition of Atorvastatin to Methotrexate therapy in patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis resulted in significantly better clinical improvement, reduced

inflammatory markers, and improved functional outcomes compared to Methotrexate alone. Statins, therefore, show potential as cost-effective adjuncts in RA treatment, especially for patients with suboptimal response to conventional DMARDs. Their dual role in reducing both synovial inflammation and cardiovascular risk makes them a promising therapeutic option.

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